

low in available P and K, and have a pH of 5.1 (air-dried soil).

We applied different amounts of N with farmyard manure (FYM) and Agroplus (a liquid micronutrient fertilizer) on a Mukthi ratoon crop. The experiment was laid out in a strip-plot design, replicated three times.

Effect of nutrition on Mukthi (CTH1) ratoon rice. RRS, Brahmavar, India, 1991 rabi.

Treatment ^a	Tillers/hill (no.) at 21 DAR ^b	Grains/panicle (no.)	Grain wt/panicle (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
F ₁ 0	7.0	46.1	0.67	1.6
F ₁ AP	6.4	48.6	0.73	1.7
F ₁ FYM	7.2	50.6	0.75	1.9
F ₂ 0	11.0	57.4	0.88	2.3
F ₂ AP	11.6	59.4	0.93	2.5
F ₂ FYM	12.2	56.7	0.87	2.3
F ₃ 0	14.4	61.2	0.95	2.7
F ₃ AP	15.2	65.2	1.04	3.0
F ₃ FYM	15.6	62.1	0.98	2.8
F ₄ 0	13.4	56.5	0.88	2.7
F ₄ AP	14.2	56.2	0.89	2.8
F ₄ FYM	14.0	55.4	0.87	2.7

For fertilizer levels

S.Em ±	0.2	0.7	0.02	0.1
LSD (0.05)	0.8	2.3	0.07	0.2
CV (%)	6.0	4.0	7.00	9.0

For AP and FYM

S.Em ±	0.1	0.9	0.01	0.02
LSD (0.05)	0.2	ns	ns	0.1
CV (%)	1.0	5.0	5.0	2.0

For interaction

For comparing two nutrition means at the same level of fertilizer	-	-	-	-
S.Em ±	-	-	-	0.1
LSD (0.05)	-	-	-	0.3

For comparing two fertilizer means at the same level of nutrition	-	-	-	-
S.Em ±	-	-	-	0.1
LSD (0.05)	-	-	-	0.2
CV (%)	6.0	4.0	5.0	5.0

^aF₁ = 0-25-25 kg NPK/ha, F₂ = 25-25-25 kg NPK/ha, F₃ = 50-25-25 kg NPK/ha, F₄ = 75-25-25 kg NPK/ha, AP = Agroplus 2 ml/liter at 15 DAR, FYM = 2.5 t/ha on ratooning day, 0 = control ^bDays after ratooning.

Results showed that fertilizer levels up to 50 kg N/ha increased grain yield (see table). FYM and Agroplus had a marginal effect on the crop at all N levels. Tillers per hill, grain number, and weight per panicle showed a trend similar to that of grain yield. The ratoon crop matured in

70 d; the preceding main crop took 102 d and yielded 3.9 t grain/ha.

Mukthi can be ratoon-cropped successfully by applying 50 kg N/ha; it can be harvested about a month earlier than the main crop. ■

Influence of green manures on P use efficiency in rice

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We studied the effect of green manure crops cowpea *Vigna unguiculata*, dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata*, and sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea* on P use efficiency in rice cultivar PR106 compared with a fallow field over 2 yr. We incorporated 60-d-old unfertilized green manure into soil 1 d before

transplanting rice. Rice received 0, 13, or 26 kg P/ha as single superphosphate along with a basal dose of 120 kg N/ha as urea and 50 kg K/ha as muriate of potash. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Results were based on total dry matter accumulation and total P uptake by green manures. Sunn hemp produced the most dry matter and contained relatively higher amounts of P (see table).

Rice grain yield was significantly higher in cowpea-manured plots and lowest in fallow plots (see figure). The rice crop responded significantly to 13 kg P/ha in green-manured plots and to 26 kg P/ha in fallow plots, showing the beneficial effects of green manures as substitutes for fertilizer P in rice (see figure).

Cowpea-manured plots produced the highest yield at 6 t grain/ha with 13 kg P/ha, perhaps because cowpea decomposes

Effect of green manure and applied P on rice grain yield (av of 2 yr). Ludhiana, India.

Dry matter accumulation, total P uptake by various green manure crops, and fertilizer P use efficiency of rice as affected by various green manures. Ludhiana, India.

Green manure crop	Dry matter produced (t/ha)		Total P uptake (kg/ha)		Fertilizer P use efficiency of rice ^a (kg grain/kg applied P)	
	1st yr	2d yr	1st	2d yr	13 kg applied P/ha	25 kg applied P/ha
Cowpea	4.25	3.92	12.3	11.1	108 (41)	41 (21)
Dhaincha	3.99	3.04	11.4	8.7	85 (18)	54 (34)
Sunn hemp	5.00	4.52	12.2	11.2	89 (22)	49 (29)
Fallow	-	-	-	-	67	20
LSD (0.05)	0.57	0.59	ns	2.6		

^aAv of 2 yr. Values in parentheses show increase in P use efficiency over fallow plots.

relatively fast compared with sunn hemp and dhaincha. Every kilogram of P applied at 13 kg/ha produced 108 kg grain in cowpea, 85 in dhaincha, 89 in

sunn hemp, and 67 in fallow plots, showing an increase of 18-41 kg grain/kg P over fallow plots (see table).

Green manuring saved about 13 kg P/

ha and contributed to extra grain yield. Cowpea was the best green manure crop for rice. ■

Crop management

Effect of tillage on physical properties of soil and yield of peanut in a rice-based cropping system

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Farmers in southern India, particularly in Andhra Pradesh, grow peanut after wet season puddled rice. In the rhizosphere, peanut requires a physical environment entirely different from that of rice. Inadequate peanut seedbed preparation in puddled soils results in poor germination, plant stand, growth, and yield.

We studied the effect of five tillage methods (see table) for irrigated peanut after puddled rice during 1988-89 and 1989-90 wet seasons. The experiment

was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications in a sandy loam soil with 0.11% organic C.

Plowing was deeper in the tractor-drawn treatment. Mean weight diameter (MWD) of seed zone aggregates varied among the tillage treatments. MWD, with many clods, was highest with the country plow. The rototiller treatment had small and relatively uniform aggregates.

Tillage affected germination. It was highest with the rototiller, where aggregate sizes favored good seed-soil contact and the highest soil moisture content. Soil penetration resistance recorded at pegging stage was least in the rototiller treatment. Haulm and pod yields were highest in the tractor-drawn treatment, closely followed by those with the rototiller.

The higher yields obtained with tractor tillage compared with bullock-drawn treatments might be due to the deeper plowing, which resulted in breaking of

the subsoil hardpan layer and smaller aggregates. Higher yields with rototillage were due to uniform aggregate size and low soil strength (penetration resistance).

We suggest that farmers use rototillage when growing peanut after puddled rice in light-textured soils because of the relative ease of operation, low cost, and higher yields. ■

Effect of tillage on physical properties of soil and yield of peanut. Hyderabad, India, 1988 and 1989.

Treatment	Plowing depth (cm)	Mean weight diameter (cm)	Soil moisture ^a (% wt/wt)	Germination (%)	Penetration resistance at pegging stage (kg/cm ²)	Yield (t/ha)	
						Haulm	Pod
T1 Plowing twice with bullock-drawn, country plow	7.0	4.5	7.4	47	35	2.39	1.44
T1 + disc harrow twice, bullock drawn	7.1	3.0	7.9	51	33	2.52	1.45
T1 + disc harrow 4 times, bullock drawn	7.8	2.3	7.2	52	35	2.54	1.70
T1 + rototiller twice, power tiller drawn	7.6	1.6	11.3	57	29	3.13	1.90
T5 Disc plow once + disc harrow once, tractor drawn	12.9	3.0	10.7	55	31	3.20	1.96
LSD (0.05)	-	-	1.3	6	1	0.35	0.11

^aSoil moisture at 20 d after sowing.

Evaluation of rice planting methods for rainfed lowlands of Karnataka

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Rice is normally sown with a seed drill in the rainfed lowlands of interior Karnataka. Sowing dry seed on moist soil with the onset of the monsoon (DSR-moist) is the common practice, with dry sowing on dry soil (DSR-dry) seen in some areas. Wet sowing can be difficult

Grain yield and net profit as influenced by planting methods of rice in rainfed lowlands of Karnataka, India, 1990 and 1991 kharifs.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Net profit (\$/ha)	
	1990	1991	1990	1991
Wet sown without fertilizer	4.3	F	10.7	F
Wet sown with fertilizer	5.6	F	13.6	F
Dry sown without fertilizer	N	4.5	N	14.5
Dry sown with fertilizer	5.2	6.1	12.4	21.2
Line transplanted with fertilizer	5.0	5.6	10.8	17.2
Broadcast pre-germinated seeds with fertilizer	1.8	F	0.9	F
LSD (0.05)	1.2	1.3		

^aN = treatment not included, F = failed treatment.